
Reversal of Social Order during Festivities in As You like It

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Abstract

The upheaval in a social order which results in the reversals of the established norms of the s and traditions of the society is a hallmark of Shakespearean plays like As You Like It. However such reversals in the social order are of a temporary nature, they usually take place during times of festivities. During the festivities people shed their inhibitions due to the liberal and fun filled atmosphere and make fun of the established social and political order. The aforementioned situation is ably depicted in Shakespeare's As You Like It. The object of present paper is to discuss the reversal of social order during festivities in AS YOU LIKE IT.

Keywords: Social problems, Existential Concerns, Art of Characterization

As You Like It is based on festivity and festivity during Shakespeare's lifetime was associated with days of the year set aside for holidays and celebrations. Holidays and festivals like the 'Lord of Misrule' was celebrated in various parts of England where a person would be crowned as a mock king (known as Lord of Misrule) and he in turn would choose his courtiers. Then the mock king and his mock courtiers would dress themselves in gaudy clothes, jewels and march across the village, dancing and making a lot of noise. The celebration of this festival was associated with the reversal of the social hierarchy. People could mock the King, Queen and the clergy while celebrating such festivals. It seems that during holidays and celebrations there was a license to transgress the boundaries of social norms. Therefore holidays and celebrations were meant to forget social norms and restrictions.

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In As You Like It, the Duke is shown to be living in a forest after being banished from his kingdom. The Duke and his Lords pass their time in the Forest of Arden, by dancing,

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organizing banquets and masques. There is absence of work and the King and his followers survive on whatever they get in the Forest. Thus the Duke, who is of royal parsonage and has lived in the arms of comfort, seems to be enjoying his simple existence in the Forest. This is a clear example of reversal of social order. Similarly, Rosalind violates the code of gender distinction by dressing up as a man. During the Elizabethan period, women were not allowed to act on stage and therefore a man dressed as a woman enacted a female role. By dressing up as a male, Rosalind is entering a domain reserved for men only. But violation of established norms was only possible during festivities. Rosalind decides to retain her disguise even after reaching the Forest of Arden because of the festive atmosphere prevalent there. But the reversal of the social order is temporary. The end of festivity also signifies the end of all the social upheavals associated with it. In the end of this comedy, the Duke gets his crown back and starts preparing to go back to his luxurious dwellings and Rosalind decides to do away with her disguise. Shakespeare has tried to prove that the changes that take place during festivity are not permanent but temporary. The Duke's brother, Frederick, usurps his throne and banishes him from the kingdom. The Duke and his Lords take shelter in the Forest of Arden. According to the Duke, the Forest is a safer place than the court. He says, "Are not these woods more free from peril than the envious court"¹. This quote proves that the Duke finds the Forest better than the court. But the Duke and his Lords are high-minded people, accustomed to live in the lap of luxury. It is difficult to believe how they could like living in harsh conditions especially when he says,

"The seasons' difference, as the icy fang
And the churlish chiding of the winter's wind,
Which when it bites and blows upon my body"². (Act II, scene i, 6-8)

But the Duke finds the simple life of Forest better than life at the court because he is away from the tension and politics prevalent in the court. The Duke also likes staying in Arden because he is free from his tyrannical brother. "The first half of *As You Like It*, beginning with tyrant brother and tyrant Duke and moving out into the Forest, is chiefly concerned with the establishing this sense of freedom; the traditional contrast of court and country is developed in a way that is shaped by the contrast between everyday and holiday"³ Therefore, the Duke likes living in the Forest of Arden because he has freedom to do what he wants; he is not under the control of his brother. Similarly, there is practically no work to do in the Forest. The Duke and his Lords do not have the responsibility of official work and therefore they have enough time to enjoy themselves. During a holiday or a celebration, people do not do any work; they mainly enjoy themselves. A similar kind of situation exists in the Forest, where the Duke and the Lords spend time in arranging banquets and gathering food. Thus an atmosphere of festivity exists in the Forest of Arden. There is a lack of social hierarchy in the Forest of Arden. Even though the Duke and the Lords belong to the aristocratic class, they have no qualms in gathering food in the Forest. The Duke and his men are happy in having a banquet in the middle of a forest. When Orlando interrupts the Duke's banquet in Act II, Scene vii, the Duke invites him to join the banquet. The Duke's invitation to Orlando is a clear example of the festive atmosphere existing in the Forest, where there is no place for conflict. Similarly, Celia and Rosalind (who is disguised as Ganymede) decide to buy a cottage and pasture and a flock of sheep in the Forest. Celia and Rosalind belong to a royal family but they nevertheless decide to settle down in the Forest as shepherds. This is an example of the reversal of social

hierarchy during a festive period. Celia and Rosalind have left the palace where their actions were governed by social norms and have reached the Forest of Arden, where a condition of festivity exists. In Arden, there are no societal restrictions on Celia and Rosalind; they are away from the control of the tyrannical Frederick and are free to do anything. The atmosphere of festivity in the Forest accentuates this freedom. This freedom in turn destroys the social barriers that normally exist in a society. This is the reason why Celia and Rosalind befriend the shepherd Corin and meddle in the affairs of Silvius. Consequently the atmosphere of festivity in the Forest results in the collapse of social hierarchy.

Rosalind dresses up as a man in order to escape from Frederick's tyranny. But on reaching the Forest of Arden, she does not remove her disguise but on the contrary uses it to befool people and have fun. But Rosalind's disguise is also a revolt against the patriarchal system. Frederick is the patriarch in the palace, he orders Rosalind to leave the palace or else face fatal consequences. By dressing as a man, Rosalind is mocking the authority of Frederick and in turn she is challenging the patriarchal system. But Rosalind is able to dress up as a man and reverse the gender role because she is in the Forest of Arden where there are no social constraints and she is free to do anything. According to Penny Gay, "As You Like It effects, through Rosalind's behaviour, the most thorough deconstruction of patriarchy and its gender roles in the Shakespearean canon; yet it is a carnival license allowed only in the magic space of the greenwood"⁴. Thus the atmosphere of festivity in the forest gives Rosalind a license to dress up as a man.

Shakespeare has cleverly portrayed the temporary nature of festivity in The Forest of Arden. The Duke and the Lords live like commoners in the forest, without any comfort or luxury. But this reversal of the social order is temporary. Ultimately, Frederick decides to return back the throne to the Duke. The Duke has got back his original royal status. He is no longer a commoner living in the Forest. By depicting the reversal of the Duke's fortune, Shakespeare has shown that the change in the social conditions of the people during a festival or a holiday is temporary. The license of transgressing social codes is also temporary. This is the reason why Rosalind reveals her true identity in the end of the play. The revelation of Rosalind's true identity signals an end to the fun she was having with Orlando, Phoebe and Silvius. As Rosalind's disguise was temporary, the collapse of social codes during the time of festivity is also temporary. This is the main reason why people were allowed to flout social norms during festive seasons because it was known that such an upheaval was temporary and society would revert back to its original position after the completion of festivities.

The Duke's banishment, Rosalind and Celia's escape and the enmity between Orlando and Oliver are serious issues. Shakespeare could have easily used such a plot to produce a tragic or a serious play. But Shakespeare exploits the festive atmosphere in the Forest. During festive seasons, people celebrated and enjoyed themselves. Conflicts were forgotten and people endeavored to have fun. Similarly, in the Forest of Arden, everyone is enjoying. People have forgotten their conflicts and fights and are passing away their time by singing and dancing. The enmity between Orlando and Oliver comes to an end in the Forest, Frederick returns back Duke senior's throne and Rosalind and Celia start making plans to return to the palace. All the serious issues mentioned above in the paragraph are peacefully resolved. Thus the reversal of social order during an atmosphere of festivity never accentuates conflict but on the contrary diffuses any kind of quarrel or squabble.

Endnotes

1. William Shakespeare, *As You Like It* (Delhi: S. Chand & Company Ltd, 1999), p. 34.
2. *ibid.*
3. C.L. Barber, *Shakespeare's Festive Comedy: A Study of Dramatic Form and Its Relation to Social Custom* (New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1959), p. 223.
4. Penny Gay, *As She Likes It: Shakespeare's Unruly Women* (London: Routledge, 1994), p. 49.

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